

**THE EFFECT OF MOTIVATION, JOB SATISFACTION AND
JOB DISCIPLINE TOWARD EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE OF
PT. BUMA PERINDAHINDO AT LNG TANGGUH SITE,
TELUK BINTUNI REGENCY, WEST PAPUA, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

The Effect of Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline on Employee Performance at PT. Buma Perindahindo at LNG Tangguh Site, Kabupaten Teluk Bintuni – Papua Barat. This study aimed to examine on partially and simultaneously the effects of motivation (X1), job satisfaction (X2), work discipline (X3) on the employee performance (Y) at PT. Buma Perindahindo LNG Tangguh site, West Papua. The samples were taken as many as 97 employees selected by saturated sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaire while data analysis used multiple linear regression. Partially result this study proved that motivation (X1) have a significant effect on employee performance (Y) for 14.3 %, job satisfaction (X2) have a significant effect on employee performance (Y) for 10.6%, while work discipline (X3) gave an insignificant effect on employee performance (Y) for 3.8%. Simultaneously result Motivation (X1), job satisfaction (X2), work discipline (X3) have a significant effect on employee performance (Y) for 26.3%.

Keywords: motivation, satisfaction, discipline and employee performance

1. Introduction

The company is a series of systems and human activities that work together. At the same time, the company is said to be a coordination that organizes the activities of several people to achieve some common goals through the division of work and function through the hierarchy of authority and responsibility (Schein in Mangkunegara, 2001).

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The importance of motivation to improve employee performance is seen from Ichlapio et al (2016) study which states that motivation partially have positive and significant effect on employee performance. Because motivation is very important role in influencing the level of ability in carrying out its function, so that the harmonious atmosphere can encourage work performance.

In addition to motivation, job satisfaction should also be the company's attention because job satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or excitement of someone before and after doing a job. If employees feel happy in working, then the results of his work will be good. Similarly, if a person is not happy in his work, it will also affect the work of employees. Thus, job satisfaction can affect performance.

This is supported by the research of Rizki and Hajan (2013), stated that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. Employees always want a payment system and a fair promotional policy is not a double meaning and in line with their expectations. When payments are deemed fair based on job demands, individual skill levels, and prevailing wage standards, high satisfaction will arise.

A disciplined employee will reflect the great sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him. Job discipline is the effort of employees to carry out their work activities seriously. Job discipline in this case can take the form of time, for example coming to work on time. Then discipline in doing what is ordered to him in accordance with the command to be done.

In the research of Hermansyah and Indarti (2015), stated the results of research had proved that there was a significant effect between job discipline and employee performance. While discipline had a high role in improving employee performance. Good job discipline reflects the extent of a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him by all the rules drafted by the company. Employees who behave disciplined usually will succeed in the job because they are able to set what the priorities are so that their performance will also be good.

PT. Buma Perindahindo Indonesia is a company that has been trying to solve the human resource problem which is the task of the personnel department. Another thing that is noticed by the company is to provide motivation in completing the work where it exceeds the specified job target so that employees can receive rewards from the company. However, in some cases contradictory conditions are found in the workplace, where employees experience saturation due to monotonous work, long on-site schedule at work, incident in the field caused by human error. Based on preliminary observations made by the writers, it was found that the performance of employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo was quite good; it was supported by the level of absenteeism and employee performance.

As a company that runs the function of human resource management, employee performance decline in PT. Buma Perindahindo also happened. This was indicated by the decreasing working hours, some less than 11 hours of work but others reaching the target. Working hour applied by the company was until 18:00 WIT, but oftentimes employees were out of plant area 2 hours earlier. Based on interviews with Project

Manager and Personnel Manager as well as Field Supervisors of PT. Buma Perindahindo there were some problems that convey, namely workload and employee's job satisfaction.

2. Problem Formulation

Based on the above background, the formulation of the problem was as follows:

1. Partially, was there a significant effect of motivation on employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo?
2. Partially, was there a significant effect of job satisfaction on the employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo?
3. Partially, was there a significant effect of job discipline on the employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo?
4. Simultaneously, was there a significant effect of motivation, job satisfaction and job discipline on the employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo?

2.1 Research Objective

Based on the research background and problem, the objectives to be achieved in this research were:

1. To test and analyze partially the significant effect of motivation on employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo;
2. To test and analyze partially the significant effect of job satisfaction on employee performance PT. Buma Perindahindo;
3. To test and analyze partially the significant effect of the job discipline on the employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo;
4. To test and analyze simultaneously the significant effect of motivation, job satisfaction and job discipline on the employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo.

3. Literature Review

Henry Fayol's approach is based on administrative management, which means an approach from top managers to low-level managers. While the approach used by Frederick Winslow Taylor is based on the operative management approach from low managers to top managers. The emphasis is on the efficiency and productivity of the executives at the lower levels.

Three public administration theories influenced by the private or business sector are: 1) Performance management, 2) New Public Management (NPM), 3) New Public Service (NPS). Robbins (2007), defined motivation as a process of intensity, direction, and perseverance of an individual to achieve his goal. Motivation is the result of interaction between the individual and the situation. Noe et al (2011), job satisfaction is an atmosphere of happy feelings from members of the organization as a response to the

perception that someone's job meets the standard of work. Faustino (2010), Discipline is the norm and rule applied by organizations to members of the organization because of a disciplinary action. Gibson et al (2014), said that individual performance was the basis of organizational performance that was strongly influenced by individual characteristics, individual motivation, expectation, and judgment made by management on achievement of individual performance outcomes.

4. Research Methods

4.1 Research Approach

A good methodology should bring the researcher to achieve the objective (Dalle et al., 2017; Dalle & Baharuddin, 2017). The research approach used was explanatory research with quantitative approach. This study described the same data in which the researcher explains the causal relationship between the variables through hypothesis testing.

4.2 Research Type

Type of causality research was research conducted with the intent to analyze the effect among variables. Variables (X) in this research were Job Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Job Discipline, and variable (Y) is Employee Performance. Each variable had an indicator that would be tested through the question instrument of the questionnaire distribution tested with the validity and reliability tests.

4.3 Research Location

The location used as an object in this research was PT. Buma Perindahindo Civil Maintenance No. Contract 4400000589 LNG Tangguh Plant –Teluk Bintuni, West Papua Province.

5. Population and Research Sample

5.1 Population

In this research, the population was employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo with the total of 97 people with various classifications of positions. Arikunto (2006), if the subject of research was less than 100 then the whole was a population research.

5.2 Sample

The sampling technique used was a saturated sampling technique. While the entire population was to be made a sample. The number of populations was taken all because the consideration of all samples could be reached and used as research respondents.

6. Data Collection Technique

Data collection techniques used was collecting data directly with field research method by distributing questionnaires to employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo Civil Maintenance No. Contract 4400000589 LNG Tangguh Plant –Teluk Bintuni, West Papua. Province.

6.1 Type of data in use

1. Primary data

Primary data came from respondents who were employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo Civil Maintenance No. Contract 4400000589 LNG Tangguh Plant - Teluk Bintuni, West Papua Province, obtained from the distribution of questionnaires to respondents.

2. Secondary data

Secondary data used came from the office of PT. Buma Perindahindo Civil Maintenance No. Contract 4400000589 LNG Tangguh Plant - Teluk Bintuni, West Papua Province.

6.2 Validity and Reliability Tests

Validity test was done to measure the validity of a questionnaire. If the questionnaire was valid then the question was able to reveal something to be measured. All statements had r count $>$ r table value of 0.361 so it could be concluded that all statements were declared valid. Based on the results of reliability test all variables must had coefficient of alpha Cronbach above 0.70 so it could be concluded all the variables were declared reliable.

6.3 Data Analysis Technique

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the influence of independent variable to dependent variable. The equations used were:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3$$

Information:

Y = Performance;

X1 = Motivation;

X2 = Job satisfaction;

X3 = Job discipline;

a = Constants.

6.4 Partial Regression Coefficient Test (T Test)

T Test was done to find out how far the influence of a variable was not bound partially (individual) to variation of bound variable.

6.5 Simultaneous Regression Coefficient Test (F Test)

Regression coefficient test was simultaneously done (F Test) to know the influence of unrelated variable (X1) motivation, (X2) job satisfaction, and (X3) job discipline simultaneously to the dependent variable namely (Y) employee performance.

7. Result and Discussion

7.1 Overview of Research Objects

PT. Buma Perindahindo is a contractor company engaged in oil and gas based in Papua more precisely in Sorong - West Papua, and has branch offices in Timika, Biak, Jakarta, Surabaya, participated in the development of the Nation in general and the area of West Papua in particular.

7.2 Vision, Mission, and Values of PT. Buma Perindahindo

Main Vision: To be the best contractor from Papua that operates internationally with professional standards.

Vision and Mission of PT. Buma Perindahindo from various aspects are:

1. From the service aspect, PT. Buma Perindahindo provides the best service to clients;
2. From the aspect of Safety and Safety, PT. Buma Perindahindo provides services that prioritize safety aspects for the convenience of customers / clients;
3. From the aspect of People, PT. Buma Perindahindo builds employee competence especially local Papuan employees to be proud to work professionally;
4. From the aspect of Team Work, PT. Buma Perindahindo puts forward that working in a solid team and builds each other;
5. From aspect Growth, PT. Buma Perindahindo develops its business, especially the development of offshore industry resources;
6. From the impact, PT. Buma Perindahindo gives a positive influence on the community and company environment.

7.3 Values of PT. Buma Perindahindo

1. Integrity; it is a behavior that raises trust;
2. Persistence; it always looks for solutions in each problem and never gives up;
3. Team Work; it always coordinates well;
4. Safety; it promotes a major safety culture;
5. Excellence; it provides best service of Cost, Quality, and Time.

8. Research Results

Questionnaires that would be used as a data gathering tool was first conducted an experimental research instrument. Testing conducted was the test of validity and

reliability. This test was intended to measure the level of accuracy and reliability of the questionnaire as a data collection tool.

8.1 Characteristics of Respondents

8.1.1 Characteristics of Respondents by Sex

Table 1: Respondent Characteristics Based on Sex

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Man	95	97.9%
Woman	2	2.1%
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this research was known that 97.9% of respondents were male, and 2.1% of respondents were female. With that percentage, it could be said that based on the gender of the respondents who participated in the study there were more men than women.

8.1.2 Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 30 years old	23	23.7 %
31 – 40 years old	48	49.5 %
41 – 50 years old	24	24.7 %
51 – 60 years old	2	2.1 %
60 years old	0	0
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this study found that 23.7% of respondents aged 20-30 years, and dominated by 49.5% of respondents aged 31-40 years, 24.7% of respondents aged 41-50 years, the remaining 2.1% of respondents aged 51-60 years. This shows that most of PT. Buma Perindahindo employees are 41-50 years old.

8.1.3 Characteristics of Respondents Based on Marital Status

Table 3: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	76	78.4%
Not Married	21	21,6 %
Widow/Widower	0	0
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this research noted that 78.4% of respondents had married status, and 21.6% of respondents had status of 'not married'. This suggested that based on the marital status of research respondents there were more respondents who had married status than those who had not married.

8.1.4 Characteristics of Respondents Based on Latest Education

Table 4: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Latest Education

Latest Education	Frequency	Percentage
SMP	7	7.2%
SMA	79	81.5%
Diploma III	0	0
S1/DVI	11	11.3%
S2	0	0
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this study found that 7.2% had junior high school education, and 81.5% of respondents had a recent high school education, and 11.3% of respondents had a recent education under Strata-1.

8.1.5 Characteristics of Respondents by Income

Table 5: Characteristics of Respondents by Income

Income	Frequency	Percentage
<2.500.000	0	0
2.500.000 – 5.000.000	0	0
5.100.000-7.500.000	18	18.6%
7.501.000 -10.000.000	62	63.9%
>10.000.000	17	17.5%
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this study found that 18.6% earned 5,100,000-7,500,000, and 63.9% of respondents earned 7,501,000-10,000,000, and 17.5% of respondents earned above 10,000,000. This indicated that most Employees had income between 7,501,000 and 10,000,000.

8.1.6 Characteristics of Respondents Based on Working Duration

Table 6: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Working Duration

Working Duration	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 year	2	2.1%
1,1-3 years	5	5.1%
3,1-5 years	23	23.7%
5,1 -7 years	35	36.1%
>7,1 years	32	33%
Total	97	100%

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the above table, from 97 employees of PT. Buma Perindahindo who participated in this research noted that 2.1% have been working in the company for <1 year, and 5.1% of respondents have been working for 1.1-3 years, and 23.7% of respondents have been working for.

8.2 Perception of Respondents

8.2.1 Perception of Respondents on Job Motivation Variable

Perception of respondents on work motivation variable above can be seen that from 97 respondents, for the indicator of job achievement most of respondents (64.9%) agreed that their achievements were now very satisfactory and only 16.5% of respondents stated strongly agreed, the average item was equal to 3.95 showed that most respondents agreed that achievement has been satisfactory.

Then from 97 respondents, for the question items that the Company cared for achievements, most of respondents (55.7%) agreed, and only 21.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.91 which indicated most respondents agreed that the Company was concerned with the achievement of the work achieved.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, for the item that the Company provided an opportunity to obtain a higher position, most of respondents (60.8%) agreed, and 24.7% of respondents stated strongly agreed. An average of this item was 4.05 which indicated most respondents agreed that the Company provided an opportunity to obtain a higher position.

Then from 97 respondents, for self-improvement indicator, the result was most of respondents (53.6%) stated strongly agreed, and 44.3% of respondents only agreed. The average of this indicator item was 4.52 which indicated most respondents stated strongly agreed that they wanted to develop capability during the work in the company.

Next of 97 respondents, for the question item that rarely got the opportunity to follow training for career progress and self-development, most of respondents (32.0%) agreed, and 28.9% of respondents stated disagreed. The average of this item was 3.11

which showed that most respondents said it was normal to rarely get a chance to attend training for career advancement and self-development.

Then from 97 respondents, from self-development question, most of respondents (47.4%) stated disagreed and only 20.6% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 2.92 which showed that most respondents stated that they had been given the opportunity to attend training to develop themselves but not as expected.

Furthermore, for indicator of work itself (the work itself), from 97 respondents, most of respondents (51.5%) agreed, and 25.8% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.93 which showed that most respondents agreed with the statement that the work itself strongly challenged them to do their best.

Still with work itself indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (62.9%) agreed, and 20.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.01 showed most respondents agreed that employees always found new methods to facilitate the work undertaken.

Next of 97 respondents, the ability to simplify difficult working procedures became easier, most of respondents (49.5%) agreed, and 29.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. An average of this item was 4.08 indicated that most respondents agreed that employees were able to simplify difficult working procedures easier.

Then from 97 respondents, for indicator of recognition, most of respondents (55.7%) agreed, and 30.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.13 showed most respondents agreed that in the workplace the employees got fair treatment and appreciated.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents with the question that the result of the work was assessed objectively by the Company, 60.8% of respondents agreed, and 29.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.15 showed that most respondents agreed that their work was assessed objectively by the Company.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (57.7%) agreed that employees got recognition and awards when successfully doing a good job, and 15.5% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.73 showed that most respondents agreed that employees received recognition as well as rewards when successfully doing the job well.

Next to Company Policy indicator (company policy), from 97 respondents, most of respondents (69.1%) agreed that employees already understood well Corporate Regulations both already socialized and as stated in specified time employment agreement (STEA), and 21.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed, Average of this item amounted to 4.08 indicated most respondents agreed that employees already understood well Corporate Regulations both that had been socialized as well as contained in the STEA.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (59.8%) agreed that they were able to implement company regulations properly and responsibly, and 38.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.36 showed that most

of the respondents stated that they were able to implement the company's rules well and responsibly.

Furthermore, for the question item that in the workplace they considered colleagues as part of the family, the result was 97 respondents where most of respondents (63.9%) stated strongly agreed, and 33.0% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 4.61 showed most respondents stated strongly agreed that during the workplace considered colleagues as family.

Then for the indicator of Relationship with peers, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed that they could foster good and wide cooperation with all people who had working relationship and who had no working relationship, and 43.3% strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.33 showed most respondents agreed that they could foster good and broad cooperation with all people who had a working relationship or a non-working relationship.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (66.0%) agreed to be able to convey information both in verbal way and in written clearly and systematically with colleagues, and 30.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.28 showed that most of the respondents agreed to be able to convey information both in verbal way and in written clearly and systematically with colleagues.

Then from 97 respondents, 61.9% of respondents agreed that they could complete the work with team work, and 32.0% of respondents stated strongly agreed. An average of this item was 4.55 indicated that most respondents stated that they were able to complete the work with team work.

Furthermore, work security indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (51.5%) agreed that the work environment situation was good and fun, and 30.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.12 showed most respondents stated that the current work environment situation was good and fun.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (52.6%) agreed that safety was guaranteed by the Company, and 37.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.42 showed that most respondents stated that work safety was guaranteed by the Company.

Of the 97 respondents, 55.7% of respondents said they did not agree that they were not threatened with termination of employment, and 26.8% of respondents stated strongly disagreed. The average of this item was only 2.02 indicated that most respondents felt threatened by termination of employment.

Then indicator Relationship with supervisor (Relationship with superior), from 97 respondents most of respondents (44.3%) agreed that Leaders always gave encouragement and spirit to work better, and 36.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.07 indicated that most respondents agreed that their Leaders always gave encouragement and spirit to work better.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (55.7%) agreed that the working relationship between superiors with subordinates good and not rigid, while 24.7% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.97

indicated most respondents agreed that the relationship between superior and subordinate was good and not rigid.

Then still with the indicator of relationship with superior, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (49.5%) agreed that superiors always communicated with subordinates everything related to the business achievement of duties, and 35.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. Average of this item was 4.15 showed most respondents agreed that superiors always communicated with subordinates everything related to the effort of achieving the task.

Next, Salary indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (54.6%) agreed that the salary could give the motivation to work better, and 37.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.25 showed that most respondents agreed that salary could give motivation to work better.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (54.6% agreed that receiving salary on time, and 40.2% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.33 showed most respondents agreed that receiving a salary on time.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (44.3%) agreed that the amount of salary obtained in accordance with the work done, and 20.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed and normal. The average of this item was 3.69 showed that most respondents agreed that the salary obtained in accordance with the work performed.

8.2.2 Perception of Respondents on Job Satisfaction Variable

Perception of Respondents on job satisfaction variable above, could be known for loyalty indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed that the problem in company organization was employee's problem also, while 25.8% respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.39 showed most respondents agreed that the problem in the organization of the company was the employee's problem as well.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (46.4%) stated strongly agreed that doing the job with all the heart and responsible, and 45.4% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 4.38 showed that most respondents agreed that doing work with all their hearts and responsibilities.

Furthermore, of the 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed that it felt better to be in one organization to spend most of their career, and 22.7% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.69 showed that most respondents agreed that it felt better to be in one organization to spend most of their career.

Then the indicator of ability, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (46.4%) agreed that during the work was trusted and given the task in accordance with ability, and 33.0% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.09 indicated that most respondents agreed that during the work was trusted and given the task in accordance with the ability.

Next of 97 respondents, most of respondents (56.7%) agreed that they could complete the job without any errors, on time and neat, and 22.7% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.02 showed most respondents agreed that they could complete the work without any errors, on time and neat.

Then for the honesty indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (67.0%) agreed that it had complied with all the regulations contained in the STEA (certain time employment agreement) and work regulations, and 21.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.10 showed most respondents agreed to have complied with all the regulations contained in the STEA or work regulations.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (51.5%) agreed that to be honest and frank about the work undertaken also able to explain the risk factors, and 37.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.23 showed most respondents agreed that honest and frank about the work undertaken was also able to explain the risk.

Then the indicator of creativity, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (49.5%) agreed that in working, we should be initiative and creative and, always tried to develop an existing work system, and 35.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.20 showed most respondents agreed that full of initiative, creative, always trying to develop an existing work system.

Next of the 97 respondents, 53.6% of respondents agreed that they always tried to find a way out in every job problem, and 39.2% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.32 indicated that most respondents agreed that they were always trying to find a way out of each job problem.

Then for leadership indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (37.1%) said they agreed to be motivated to be leaders for their peers, and 36.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.02 showed that most respondents said they agreed to be motivated to be leaders for their peers.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (56.7%) agreed that they could motivate their peers to work effectively, and 27.8% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.09 showed that most respondents agreed that they could motivate their co-workers to work effectively.

Then salary level indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed that the salary received was in accordance with the quality and quantity of work undertaken, and 26.8% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.54 showed most respondents agreed that the salary received was in accordance with the quality and quantity of work undertaken.

Next of 97 respondents, most of respondents (36.1%) agreed that the income received was very satisfactory, while 30.9% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.24 showed most respondents saying it was normal that the current income received had been very satisfactory.

Then indirect compensation indicator, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) stated did not agree that the incentives currently received were very satisfactory, and 21.6% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 2.55 indicated that most respondents stated that the incentives currently received were very satisfactory.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (56.7%) agreed that given rewards when completing work exceeded the target work, and 15.5% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.70 showed that most respondents agreed that rewards given when completing the work exceeded the target work.

Then for the working environment indicator, from 97 respondents most of respondents (54.6%) agreed that they could adjust to good work environment, and 36.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.26 showed most respondents agreed that it could adapt well to the work environment.

Then from 97 respondents, 51.5% of respondents agreed that the work environment was healthy and pleasant, and 36.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.24 showed most respondents agreed that the work environment was healthy and fun.

8.2.3 Perception of Respondents on Job discipline Variable

Perception of respondents on job discipline variable above, for indicator of executing and completing task in time could be seen that from 97 respondents as many as 54.6% of respondents agreed that obeying the regulations of applicable companies on site, and 40.2% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.49 showed that most respondents agreed that they were obedient to the prevailing company regulations.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (55.7%) agreed to be obedient to work roster which had been agreed in STEA (certain time agreement), and 36.1% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.28 showed that most respondents agreed to be obedient to the work roster agreed in the STEA.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (69.1%) agreed that work was done on time, and 21.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.12 showed that most respondents agreed that work was done on time.

Then for the work indicator with full initiative and creative, from 97 respondents most of respondents (52.6%) agreed that clearly understood the working procedures that had been applied, and 45.4% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.43 showed most respondents agreed to understand clearly the working procedures that had been applied.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (59.8%) agreed that always took the initiative to develop the existing work system, and 22.7% of respondents stated

strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.04 showed most respondents agreed that always took the initiative to develop an existing work system.

Then for indicator of working honestly and responsibly, from 97 respondents most of respondents (54.6%) stated strongly agreed that obedient in using PPE (personal protective equipment) according to HSE standard (health, safety and environment) in carrying out their work, and 39.2% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 4.48 showed that most respondents stated strongly agreed that obedient in using PPE according to HSE standards in carrying out their work.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed that in their work, they took the time as well as possible, and 44.3% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.37 showed that most respondents agreed that taking time as well as possible.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (52.6%) agreed to be responsible for the work equipment that had been submitted, and 42.3% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.37 showed most respondents agreed to be responsible for the work equipment that had been submitted.

Next, the indicator of going home on time, from 97 respondents of the respondents (51.5%) agreed that always kept the terms of work time on site, and 45.4% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.42 showed most respondents agreed that always kept the terms of work time on site.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (49.5%) stated strongly agreed that coming to work and returning home in accordance with the time specified, and 46.4% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 4.45 showed that most of the respondents agreed that they came to work and returned home according to the time specified.

Furthermore, from 97 respondents, most of respondents (44.3%) agreed that the working hours on site were too heavy and long, and 20.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 3.69 showed that most respondents agreed that the working hours on site were too heavy and long.

Then the indicator of behaving politely, of the 97 respondents most of the respondents (51.5%) agreed that behaved politely during working on site, and 43.3% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.38 indicated that most respondents agreed to behave politely during working on site.

Next of 97 respondents, most of respondents (55.7%) stated strongly agreed to one another respected the peers, and 40.2% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 4.52 showed most respondents stated strongly agreed to one another respected the peers.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (48.5%) agreed to one another respected the peers' skills, and 44.3% of respondents. The average of this item was 4.37 showed most respondents agreed to one another respected the peers' skills.

8.2.4 Perception of Respondents on Performance Variable

Perception of Respondents on the above performance variable, for the quality indicator it could be seen that from 97 respondents most of respondents (52.6%) stated strongly agreed that could complete the job without any errors and on time, besides that the job would be clean and neat, and 23.7% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 3.99 showed most respondents stated strongly agreed that it could complete the job without any errors and on time; besides that, the job would be clean and neat.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (42.3%) stated disagreed that they could finish the job, but the result of their work was the result of several improvements, and 22.7% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 2.69 showed that most respondents stated it was normal to finish the job, but the results of the work were the result of several improvements.

Furthermore, for the quantity indicator, from 97 respondents most of respondents (44.3%) agreed that it could complete the task exceeding the standard work that had been determined even under the time pressure situation, and 32.0% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.76 showed that most respondents agreed that it could complete the task exceeding the standard work that had been determined even under the time pressure situation.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (56.7%) agreed that they could complete the work in accordance with the specified standard, and 23.7% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.04 indicated that most respondents agreed that they could complete the work in accordance with the specified standard.

Next for the indicator of timeliness, from 97 respondents most of respondents (63.9%) agreed that capable of completing the work in accordance with the time set, and 19.6% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.03 indicating that most of the respondents agreed that they could finish the work in accordance with the time set.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (56.7%) agreed that they were able to complete additional tasks with time determined by the company, and 25.8% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.08 indicating that most respondents agreed to complete additional tasks with time determined by the company.

Furthermore, for the effectiveness indicator, from 97 respondents most of respondents (64.9%) agreed that they could perform their duties efficiently and usefully, and 28.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed that performing the task efficiently and usefully. The average of this item was 4.23 showed most respondents agreed that they could perform the task efficiently and usefully.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (40.2%) agreed that the result of work produced exceeded the average set by the company, and 32.0% of respondents stated normal. The average of this item was 3.53 indicated that most respondents

agreed that the result of the work produced exceeded the average that had been determined by the company.

The next was independence indicator; from 97 respondents most of respondents (33.0%) stated disagreed that they were able to take a decision without waiting for the leadership orders, and 29.9% of respondents agreed. The average of this item was 2.80 indicated that most respondents stated it was normal that they were able to make decisions without waiting for the leadership orders.

Then from 97 respondents, 62.9% of respondents agreed that they were able to propose ideas that supported the work, and 17.5% of respondents stated strongly agreed and normal. The average of this item was 3.96 showed that most respondents agreed that they were able to present ideas that supported the work.

Furthermore, work commitment indicator, from 97 respondents most of respondents (60.8%) agreed that they should have the ability to apply and run HSE in the workplace, and 30.9% of respondents stated strongly agreed. The average of this item was 4.21 showed that most respondents agreed that they should have the ability to apply and run HSE in the workplace.

Then from 97 respondents, most of respondents (50.5%) stated strongly agreed that they had the same goal in carrying out their duties with full responsibility, and 45.4% of respondents agreed that they had the same goal in carrying out their duties in full responsibility. The average of this item was 4.46 showed that most respondents agreed that they had the same goal in carrying out their duties in full responsibility.

8.3 Classic Assumption Test

Table 7: Assumptions of Multicollinearity

Independent Variable	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Job Motivation	0.587	1.704
Job Satisfaction	0.529	1.890
Job Discipline	0.665	1.504

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Based on the results in the table above, it could be seen all variables of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline produced VIF values smaller than 10 and tolerance values greater than 0.1. Thus, regression analysis in this study stated did not contain multicollinear symptoms.

8.4 Assumption of Normality

Table 8: Results of Assumption of Normality

	Performance
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	0.037
Probability	0.200

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

Testing of assumption of normality produced *Kolmogorov Smirnov* test statistic of 0.037 with a probability of 0.200. This result showed that the probability > *level of significant* ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant that the resulting residual was normally distributed.

8.5 The Estimation Result of Effect of Job Motivation, Job Satisfaction and Job Discipline Variables toward Performance Variable

The result of examination of the effect of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline variables toward performance variable can be seen through the following table:

Table 9: Coefficient

Variable	Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	t statistic	Prob
Constant	1.066		22.343	0.000
Job motivation	0.143	0.269	2.353	0.021
Job satisfaction	0.106	0.248	2.062	0.042
Job discipline	0.038	0.108	1.004	0.318
F statistic	= 12.433	Prob	= 0.000	
R-squared = 0.286	Adj. R-squared = 0.263			

Source: processed by primary data, 2017

8.6 Determination Coefficient Test

The amount of contribution of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline variables toward performance variable could be known through the coefficient of determination (adj R²) that was equal to 0.263 (26.3%). This meant that the diversity of performance variable could be explained by the variables of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline of 26.3%, or in other words the contribution of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline variables toward the performance variable was 26.3%, while the rest of 73.7% was a contribution of other variables which were not discussed in this study.

8.7 Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Simultaneous hypothesis test was used to know whether there was an effect of job motivation variable, job satisfaction, and job discipline toward performance variable. The criterion of test stated that if $F_{\text{count}} \geq F_{\text{table}}$ or probability < *level of significance* (α) then there was a significant effect simultaneously variable of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline toward performance variable. Hypothesis testing simultaneously yielded F_{count} of 12,433 with probability of 0.000. The test results showed the probability < *level of significance* ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant there was a significant effect simultaneously (together) of the variables of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline toward performance variable.

8.8 Partial Hypothesis Test

Partial hypothesis testing was used to determine whether there was an effect of job motivation variable, job satisfaction, and job discipline toward performance variable. The test criteria stated that if the value of $t_{\text{count}} \geq t_{\text{table}}$ or probability $< \text{level of significance}$ (α) then there was a significant effect individually and an effect of job motivation variable toward performance variable and effect of job satisfaction variable toward performance variable.

a) Partial Hypothesis Test between Job Motivation Variables toward Performance Variable

Hypothesis testing in partial variable of job motivation yielded value of t_{count} of 2,353 with probability equal to 0.021. The test results showed the probability $< \text{level of significance}$ ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant there was a significant effect of job motivation variable toward performance variable.

b) Partial Hypothesis Test of Job Satisfaction Variable toward Performance Variable

Hypothesis testing in partial job satisfaction variable resulted in value of t_{count} of 2.062 with probability of 0.042. The test results showed the probability $< \text{level of significance}$ ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant there was a significant influence of job satisfaction variable toward performance variable.

c) Partial Hypothesis Test of Job Discipline toward Performance Variable

Hypothesis testing in partial variable of job discipline yielded value of t_{count} equal to 1.004 with probability equal to 0.318. The test results showed probability $> \text{level of significance}$ ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant there was no significant effect partially on the job discipline toward performance variable.

d) Test of Partial Hypothesis of Constants toward Performance Variable

Hypothesis testing in partial constant variable yielded value of t_{count} equal to 22.343 with probability equal to 0.000. The test results showed the probability of $< \text{level of significance}$ ($\alpha = 5\%$). This meant there was a significant effect partially on constants toward performance variable.

8.9 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The regression equation from the result of multiple linear regression analysis was:

$$Y = 1.066 + 0.143X_1 + 0.106 X_2 + 0.038X_3$$

This equation showed the following:

1. The constant of 1.066 indicated that if the variable of job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline was constant (unchanged) then the change of performance variable was 1.066.
2. The coefficient of job motivation variable of 0.143 indicated that the variable of job motivation had positive and significant effect to the performance variable. This meant that higher job motivation tended to improve performance.

3. The coefficient of job satisfaction variable of 0.106 indicated that job satisfaction variable had positive and significant effect toward performance variable. This meant that higher job satisfaction was likely to improve performance, although the decrease was not significant.
4. The coefficient of job discipline variable of 0.038 indicated that the variable of work motivation had positive and insignificant effect on the performance variable. This meant that the higher job discipline tended to improve performance, although the increase was not significant.

8.10 Interpretation of Research Results

A. The Effect of Job Motivation (X1) toward Employee Performance (Y)

Results of hypothesis testing of Job Motivation (X1) toward Employee Performance (Y) at PT. Buma Perindahindo partially resulted in value of t_{count} of 2.353 with probability of 0.021. It could be concluded that Job Motivation (X1) proved to have a significant effect toward Employee Performance (Y) variable at 5% significance level. This was seen in the Coefficient of Job Motivation Variable of 0.143 indicated that the variable of job motivation had a positive and significant effect toward the performance variable, it meant that the increasing motivation of employees hence increased the Employee Performance.

B. The Effect of Job Satisfaction (X2) toward Employee Performance (Y)

Results of hypothesis testing of Job Satisfaction (X2) toward Employee Performance (Y) at PT. Buma Perindahindo partially, produced a value of t count of 2.062 with probability of 0.042. It could be concluded that Job Satisfaction (X2) proved to have a significant effect toward Employee Performance (Y) variable at 5% significance level. Because job satisfaction as one of the factors that affected employee performance. It was seen in the Coefficient result of Job Satisfaction of 0.106 indicated that job satisfaction variable had a positive and significant effect toward performance variable; it meant that the increasing of job satisfaction of employee hence tended to improve Employee Performance.

C. The Effect of Job Discipline (X3) toward Employee Performance (Y)

Results of hypothesis testing of Job Discipline (X3) toward Employee Performance (Y) at PT. Buma Perindahindo partially yielded value of t count of 1.004 with probability of 0.0318. It could be concluded that Job Discipline (X3) proved did not have significant effect on Employee Performance variable (Y) at 5% significance level. Because job discipline was one of the factors affected Performance. This was seen in the coefficient results of Job Discipline Variable of 0.038 indicated that the variable of job discipline had a positive and insignificant effect toward performance variable; this meant the higher job discipline of an employee was likely to improve Employee Performance, although the increase was not significant.

D. The Effect of Job Motivation (X1), Job Satisfaction (X2), and Job Discipline (X3) toward Employee Performance (Y)

From the results of hypothesis testing of Job Motivation (X1), Job Satisfaction (X2) and Job Discipline (X3) toward Employee Performance (Y) at PT. Buma Perindahindo simultaneously, based on simultaneous regression test (F test) showed that F_{count} was 12.433 with probability of 0.000 at 5% significance level. This meant that there was a significant effect simultaneously (together) the variables of job motivation, job satisfaction and job discipline toward performance. While the value of determination coefficient test (adj R2) was 0.263, this meant the diversity of performance variable could be explained by job motivation variable, job satisfaction, and job discipline of 26.3%, while the rest of 73.7% of Employee Performance influenced by other variables which were not discussed in this research.

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

9.1 Conclusion

Based on the analysis of studies and discussions that have been proposed, the conclusions of this study are as follows:

1. Partially, job motivation had a significant effect of 14.3% toward employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo
2. Partially, job satisfaction had a significant effect of 10.6% toward employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo
3. Partially, job discipline had no significant effect of 3.8% toward employee performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo
4. Simultaneously, job motivation, job satisfaction, and job discipline had a significant effect of 26.3%, toward Employee Performance of PT. Buma Perindahindo.

While the rest of 73.7% of Employee Performance influenced by other variables that were not discussed in this research included employee's workload and work schedule.

9.2 Recommendations

Based on the results of this research, it is recommended:

1. PT. Buma Perindahindo should maintain employees' job motivation and job satisfaction because these factors greatly affect their performance in the field. Motivation will encourage employees to work effectively and efficiently; the more motivated employees work well by paying attention to aspects of work safety will achieve the goals of vision, mission and corporate values.
2. PT. Buma Perindahindo should improve the job discipline continuously that must be controlled and monitored properly so that it will improve work safety aspect and human resource (HR) which will directly improve employee performance.

3. It is suggested to the leadership / management of the company to pay more attention and consider the employee's job satisfaction aspects in terms of incentives and rewards so that employees will indirectly be motivated to work better and discipline.
4. It is suggested that 73.6% variables that were not discussed in this research can be used as the next research proposal.

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TELUK BINTUNI REGENCY, WEST PAPUA, INDONESIA

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